

Bromometric Estimation of Formates by Oxidation with Bromine

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A rapid and simple procedure is described for volumetric determination of formate ion based on its oxidation by bromine in 20% KBr solution. The hydrobromic acid liberated during oxidation has been estimated by a standard solution of potassium bromate. The procedure is applicable to neutral formate solutions containing 20 to 100 mg. of formic acid with a precision of 0.5% or more. The interference caused by the salts of other organic acids and organic substance has also been investigated.

Several oxidants have been proposed for quantitative oxidation of formic acid. In Lieben's method¹ of titrating formic acid or formate solution with a standard solution of potassium permanganate in presence of excess of sodium or potassium carbonate the detection of end point is difficult owing to formation of oxide of manganese. Even the modified procedure of Jones² is not applicable in presence of much chloride.

The methods using mercuric chloride as oxidant are based on the equation:

Auerbach and Pluddemann³ estimated mercuric chloride consumed by titration with potassium iodide solution. Frenzen and Greve⁴ gravimetrically determined calomel produced. Fuchs⁵, Oldeman⁶ and Bose⁷ determined the acid produced. The acidimetric determination is interfered by carbon dioxide which is also a product of oxidation. Verma and Bose⁸ volumetrically estimated calomel either by titration with potassium iodate solution or iodimetrically in presence of potassium iodide thus avoiding the interference due to carbon dioxide.

The present workers for the first time used iodine as oxidant for estimation of formates⁹ either by estimating the iodine consumed or by determining the amount of hydriodic acid produced during oxidation. Joseph¹⁰ used bromine as oxidising agent for estimating formate ion. He determined the total bromide ions after the oxidation was complete. Maeder¹¹ using bromine solution as an oxidant estimated the unexpended bromine. It

1. *Monatsh.*, 1893, 14, 749.

2. *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1895, 17, 539.

3. *Arb. Kais. Gesundheitsamt.*, 1909, 30, 178.

4. *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1909, 80, 368.

5. *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1929, 78, 125.

6. *Pharm. Weekblad.*, 1931, 69, 379.

7. *This Journal*, 1958, 35, 320.

8. *Ibid.*, 1960, 37, 47; *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1961, 30, 171.

9. *This Journal*, 1961, 38, 109.

10. *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1910, 29, 1120.

11. *Apoth. Ztg.*, 1913, 27, 746.

took about 15 hours at room temperature for the bromine solution (prepared *in situ*) to oxidise the formate completely.

In the procedure described here, to the formate solution a measured excess of potassium bromate solution is added, mixture is boiled and bromine in 20% potassium bromide solution is gradually added when solution acquires distinct yellow colour, then about 10 c.c. of bromine solution is added in excess. The hydrobromic acid produced reacts with potassium bromate, later the bromine is boiled off the residual bromate is determined by adding excess of potassium iodide and sulphuric acid, and titrating the liberated iodine with a standard thio solution. The amount of potassium bromate consumed affords the hydrobromic acid produced during the reaction and thus formate present is evaluated. The reactions involved are:

1 ml. of 0.1 *N*-thio = 4.6 mg. of formic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium thiosulphate, starch, and potassium bromate used were of A. R. quality. Potassium iodide and potassium bromide were of Merck's variety and sodium formate was of B. D. H. A standard solution (*M*/60 or *N*/10 for this reaction) of potassium bromate was prepared by dissolving 2.784 g. of salt, dried for 1 hour at 120° in one litre of distilled water. Thio solutions (0.1 *N* and 0.05 *N*) and 1% aqueous starch solution were also prepared. Standard solutions of sodium formate were prepared by dissolving different amounts of the salts after drying at 100° for 1 hour. These solutions were standardised by other methods also. About 0.1 *N* bromine solution was prepared in 20% potassium bromide solution.

Procedure.—To a neutral solution (5 to 20 ml) of formate containing 20 to 90 mg. of formic acid, taken in a 250 ml conical flask, a standard solution of potassium bromate was added in a known excess. Total volume was adjusted to about 50 ml and the flask was heated on an electric heater. When boiling started, approximately 0.1 *N* bromine in 20% KBr solution was gradually added until there was a permanent yellow colour. Bromine solution (10 ml more from measuring cylinder) was added as excess and boiling was continued (3 to 5 minutes) so as to completely remove the bromine as indicated by the solution becoming colorless. Heating was then stopped and the flask was dipped in ice-cold water. When the solution attained room temperature excess of solid KI (about 2 to 3 g.) and 1 ml of starch solution were added. If solution turned blue, the iodine was precisely neutralised with 0.05 *N* thio. The contents of the flask were then acidified by adding excess of 1 *N* H_2SO_4 (about 5 ml) and liberated iodine was titrated with a standard thio sulphate solution. A blank was also carried out in a similar manner except for the addition

of formate solution. The difference between two this readings gave iodate consumed. Bromine solution, when boiled with water, produced hydrobromic acid; therefore in blank experiment also 10 ml of bromine was added. The results for evaluations of different formate solutions as recorded in Table I show that the method has precision of 0.5% or more. All estimations were carried out in duplicate.

TABLE I

Present	(mg.)	92.0	82.8	69.0	46.0	36.8	23.0
Found	(mg.)	91.77	82.8	69.0	45.77	36.8	22.88
%Error		-0.3	nil.	nil.	-0.5	Nil.	-0.5

Experiments were also carried out to study the effect of increase in the amount of water and bromine solution. Following results were obtained.

(i) To 10 ml of 0.1 *M* sodium formate solution taken, 15 ml. of *M*/30 potassium bromate solution and different amounts of water were added and formate was estimated by the method already described. Addition of water from 10 to 50 ml did not affect the results. Total volume may conveniently be kept about 50 ml.

(ii) In another set of experiments, keeping other conditions same as in (i), the amount of bromine solution was gradually increased. It was found that hydrobromic acid produced as a result of hydrolysis of bromine reacted with potassium bromate affording higher values for formate. If in the blank experiment the same quantity of bromine was added, which was used as excess in case of the experiment with formate solution, satisfactory results were obtained. Addition of bromine solution in large excess should be avoided after solution has attained permanent yellow colour. Approximately 0.1 *N* bromine solution (10 ml) should be added as excess and the same amount should be added in blank experiment to compensate for hydrobromic acid liberated due to hydrolysis of bromine. 0.1 *N* Bromine solution was prepared in 20% KBr solution, this decreased the volatility of bromine considerably; moreover the results for formate with this solution were quite reproducible.

Interferences.—The interference caused by a number of organic salts, alcohols and aldehydes has also been investigated. A summary is given below:—

(a) Addition of 1 ml of methyl or ethyl alcohol did not cause any appreciable interference.

(b) Formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, benzaldehyde and salicylaldehyde interfered with the procedure. In case of salicylaldehyde all the potassium bromate added was consumed.

(c) Addition of 0.2 g. of calcium gluconate, calcium lactate, potassium oxalate, sodium salicylate, sodium fumarate, sodium malonate, sodium aminoacetate and sodium melete caused profound interference. In case of sodium salicylate all the potassium bromate added was consumed.

(d) Addition of 0.2 g. calcium butyrate, potassium citrate and sodium salts of benzoic, acetic, propionic, boric, adipic malic, phenylacetic and phthalic acid also interfered and all the bromate added remained unchanged probably due to buffering effect of these

salts and preventing the reaction between potassium bromate and hydrobromic acid produced.

The method described is rapid as compared to that of Maeder¹¹. It is also accurate and independent of dilution effect moreover being iodometric exhibits a sharp end point. The disadvantage of the method lies in the interference due to large number of substances. In case of addition of most of the salts of other acids either low values for formate are obtained or almost all the bromate remains unreacted due to the buffering action of the added salts. The procedure is recommended for estimation of small amounts of formates when present as pure solution.

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